

EXPERIMENTAL TESTS ON PRESTRESSED RC BEAMS WITH GFRP REINFORCEMENT

Francesco Micelli, University of Salento, Italy, francesco.micelli@unisalento.it
Abdeldjelil Belarbi, University of Houston, USA, belarbi@uh.edu
Giovanni Paolo Delle Donne, University of Salento, Italy, giovannipaolo.delledonne@gmail.com
Lara Zerbe, University of Houston, USA, larazerbe8@gmail.com
Dario Vieira, University of Houston, USA, dario.ffvieira@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The corrosion of steel reinforcement in harsh environments makes the solution of traditional reinforced concrete (RC) not sustainable in terms of durability and maintenance of structures. The use of non metallic reinforcement in forms of Fiber Reinforced Polymer (FRP) bars is one of the possible solutions in order to extend the lifecycle of RC buildings, especially in coastal regions. Glass FRP (GFRP) bars are preferred due to their low cost, even if the elastic modulus is significantly lower respect to traditional steel. The research presented herein shows the effectiveness of GFRP reinforcement bars as tendons for mild prestressing applications. Six full-scale specimens were cast and tested, using GFRP bars and stirrups in place of conventional steel reinforcements. Different reinforcement ratios and pre-stressing levels were investigated. Results are shown in terms of load vs displacement curves and strain readings.

KEYWORDS

GFRP; Prestressed; Concrete; Beams; Glass; Tendons

INTRODUCTION

The durability of reinforced concrete (RC) structures is related to the susceptibility of metal reinforcements to the well-known phenomena of corrosion. Corrosion can occur in different forms, with different degrees of progression, under different environmental conditions. In all cases this susceptibility to oxidation of reinforcement produces an increase in the structural vulnerability of the elements, which therefore require restorative or replacement interventions. In highly aggressive regions this circumstance poses a serious threat to the service life of reinforced concrete constructions. One of the possible alternatives to eliminate the problem of corrosion, whether galvanic, chloride or hydrogen corrosion, for reinforcing bars, is to use nonmetallic reinforcement. For more than 50 years, scientific research has been investigating the use of FRP reinforcement as a sustainable alternative to traditional steel reinforcement (Navy et al., 1971; Weiser, 1983). Different studies are available by considering FRP rods as simple reinforcement in RC elements, but a more limited number of studies are available with reference to the use of FRP tendons for prestressed concrete (PC) beams. In this field early studies conducted by Lees (2001) have shown that the presence of FRP tendons in RC elements in aggressive environments removes the common problems of durability due to galvanic corrosion. A compendium of recommendations on the use of FRP prestressing reinforcement for flexural beams for use in bridge construction is available in (Kim et al., 2014). Another scientific study (Youakim et al., 2007) investigated the long term behavior and durability of FRP prestressed beams. The study by Lou et al. (2015) provided new information about the redistribution of flexural moments in hyperstatic FRP prestressed beams by using a numerical approach. Three types of tendons were investigated, including aramid FRP (AFRP), carbon FRP (CFRP) and prestressing steel. The results concluded that the failure mode of FRP PC beams depends on the reinforcement ratio, which can cause tendons tensile failure or concrete crushing, according to the overreinforcement or underreinforcement configurations, respect to the balanced ratio. It was seen that in presence of steel tendons, crushing of concrete is the dominant failure mode. When the FRP tendons were used as reinforcement, a different behaviour was observed in terms of cracks distribution, deformation

characteristics and neutral axis depth, compared to steel tendons. A more recent study focused on the service limit state problem of prestressed beams with FRP reinforcement, showing the peculiarities compared with the traditional use of steel reinforcement (Atutis et al., 2017). In Peng et al., (2018) design equations are provided, based on a statistical analysis of a large experimental database. Sectional analysis was approached with numerical methods by using an accurate stress block behaviour, in order to simulate the nonlinear compressive stress distribution in concrete. Based on a detailed parametric study of over 160,000 sections, simplified design equations for flexural capacity of tension-controlled section were derived from multiple regression analyses. One year later, another study (Xin et al., 2019) developed a new method for determining the transfer length for FRP tendons in prestressed concrete. The governing equations were obtained by combining the local bond-slip relationship for FRP tendons in concrete with composite beam theory. Recent studies (Slaitas et al., 2021) also investigated the post-tensioning of existing RC beam by using prestressed FRP rods or laminates as strengthening systems. A theoretical model was proposed and experimentally validated for those RC beams strengthened in service conditions under external load action with a prestressing force applied to the external FRP strengthening system. In this research mild prestressing applied to PC elements with GFRP reinforcing bars was investigated; six pre-tensioned concrete beams were designed, built and tested for this purpose. The beams were tested by varying the GFRP reinforcement ratio and the prestress levels. The load-deflection response and the failure modes are illustrated and discussed herein. The test results showed how the different reinforcement ratios affected the behavior of the beams under service and ultimate conditions. A comparison between the experimental results and the analytical predictions from the flexure theory of reinforced concrete was also performed to show the consistency of the experimental outcomes and the accuracy of the analytical results.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAMME

The experimental programme involved the construction of six full-scale concrete beams, fully reinforced with GFRP bars, both as longitudinal and transverse reinforcement (stirrups).

Reinforcement lay-out and materials properties

The length of the six full scale PC beams was 6.1 m, with a rectangular cross-section having dimensions 762×254 mm. Longitudinal reinforcement in the upper and lower sides of the cross section was introduced in forms of GFRP bars. The quality and grade of concrete was assumed to be the same in terms of design, the experimental variable was the GFRP reinforcement ratio and the prestress level. Two different diameters were used for GFRP longitudinal reinforcement, diameter of 13 mm (M13) and diameter of 16 mm (M16). Stirrups were made by using M13 GFRP rods that were shaped by the manufacturer according to the specifications of the design outcomes. By varying the diameter of the longitudinal reinforcement three different beam configurations were tested: configuration *A* in which two beams were reinforced with 8 M16 bars with a target pre-tension force of 57.8 kN equal to 36% of the ultimate strength, each (2 repetitions labeled as GFRP_8M16_1 and GFRP_8M16_2); configuration *B* in which two beams were reinforced with 16 M13 bars with a target pre-tension force of 44.5 kN equal to 40% of the ultimate strength, each (2 repetitions labeled as GFRP_16M13_1 and GFRP_16M13_2); configuration *C* in which two beams were reinforced with 16 M16 bars. In this last configuration the two beams were not a repetition, since one beam was not prestressed (GFRP_16M16_RC) and the second beam was pre-stressed with a target pre-tension force of 57.8 kN in each bar (GFRP_16M16). The choice of the level of prestressing of individual beams was obviously conditioned by the ultimate load of the GFRP bars, as well as the problem of relaxation losses, of which there is no in-depth knowledge at present, due to the lack of an adequate amount of scientific data for the tested bars. This limitation is related to creep and stress relaxation phenomena that may occur in the short and long-term period (Sá et al. 2011; Rossini et al. 2019). Although long-term relaxation does not affect the mechanical behavior of the tested beams in the present case, a real-world design scenario of GFRP-PC beams was still considered. Moreover, the danger of premature failures during the tensioning process was also an issue, so pre-tensioning force was limited to 40% and 36% of the ultimate tensile strength of M13 and M16 bars, respectively, to prevent premature ruptures during the jacking phase.

Figure 1 shows the longitudinal and transverse GFRP reinforcement layout of the beams. The geometrical and mechanical properties of the M13 and M16 rebars are shown in Table 1 as provided by the manufacturer (Sireg Geotech srl - Italy).

Figure 1 - Longitudinal (a) and transversal (b) sections of the GFRP-reinforced beams (cm)

Table 1: Short-term properties of the GFRP reinforcements by the manufacturer

GFRP rod	Nominal Diameter	Tensile Strength	Tensile Elastic Modulus	Ultimate Strain
	mm	MPa	GPa	%
M13	12.7	850	46	1.85
M16	15.9	800	46	1.74

GFRP tensioning and final prestressing

The anchorage of the GFRP bars for the application of tensioning, was entrusted to the typical truncated-conical devices of the Freyssenet type (chucks). This is basically the same anchoring device that is used for pre-tensioning or post-tensioning of traditional high-strength steel reinforcement. Control of the tension force, in the tensioning phase of the longitudinal GFRP reinforcement, was performed through the use of electrical strain gauges and along the development length of the bars, and through the placement of compressive load cells at the tension heads. In Figure 2 the strain gauges glued to the GFRP bars and the tensioning set-up are illustrated. Of course the strain gauges were put under physical protection in order to avoid damages during the concrete pouring and hardening phases.

Figure 2 - Strain gauge (a) and load cell (b) for the control of the prestressing levels

A rigid steel frame was designed and built according to the scope of this study, by avoiding deformations and other mechanical effects that could affect the tensioning of GFRP reinforcement or the geometry of the hardened PC beams. When both the steel frame and the reinforcement were ready, first the stirrups and then the rebars have been placed in the mold. Before starting the pre-tensioning operations on the beams' bars, the jacking system and the chucks' functioning were tested using a

small piece of GFRP bar. This was necessary particularly for safety reasons to ensure that no slippage would occur, even for higher values of the applied load closer to the declared ultimate tensile strength. The jacking system consisted of a hydraulic jack between two chucks at the live end, with a load cell to monitor the load, and a third chuck at the dead end. Since the test was successful performed, the pre-tensioning operations were started at the frame. Load cells were placed between the dead-end plate and the steel chucks of the GFRP bars for continuous load recording during prestressing and after casting, until the bars were cut. The same control units were used to record the data from strain gauges and load cells. The bars were prestressed individually in multiple stages, starting from the furthest ones and moving towards the center of the steel plate to guide its inflection and limit the load losses. Both an electric and manual hydraulic pump were used to power the jack. During each stage of prestressing, the bars can lose some of the prestressing force because of a redistribution of internal forces inside the steel frame. Therefore, the prestressing forces were applied step by step. Bars were prestressed up to a higher force than the target force to compensate for the losses. The loading process was performed at the different increasing stages until a force similar to the target one was reached, by accepting an error of +/- 5% respect to the target prestress force. During the jacking phase of GFRP_16M13_1, four bars broke or slipped through the chuck (Figure 3). That is due to the low transverse strength of orthotropic FRP pultruded materials associated with the matrix properties. This occurrence suggests that further efforts are needed in order to establish an adequate set-up for FRP applications. The broken bars were substituted, and two replaced M13 bars were prestressed at a lower value of 35.6 kN instead of 44.5 kN to avoid premature rupture. One of the replaced bar broke and slipped during the concrete pouring and could not be replaced. Similarly, during the casting of GFRP_16M13_2, one bar broke and could not be replaced. All the other bars for these two specimens and the remaining specimens (including the M16 bars) were prestressed to the target value. The pre-tensioning process for all stages, was planned to be completed just before casting of the concrete. During casting (Figure 3c), concrete coupons in forms of cylinders and prisms were poured to check respectively the compressive and tensile strength at different days (test days); slump test was also performed to check the concrete workability at the fresh state. After 3 days, the results of the compression tests on concrete cylinders have returned strength values higher than expected, thus on the 4th day after the casting, the GFRP bars were cut and the beams were removed from the molds. No cracks were observed during demolding.

Figure 3 - Failure of the GFRP at the loaded end (a) and inside the formwork (b); concrete pouring (c)

In order to illustrate the trend of the applied load and deformations over time, during the tensioning phases, the strain profiles recorded for beam GFRP_8M16_2 are depicted in Figure 4. In the diagrams, the caption "B" indicates that the bar is positioned in the lower side of the cross section (Bottom reinforcement), while the caption "T" indicates that the bar is positioned in the upper side of the cross section (Top). The first tensioning phase up to 30 kN (first 14 hrs) was done in order to accommodate all the strains of the steel frame and other devices used in the process. The first two peaks indicate the two jacking phases of the pre-tensioning process which were performed to reach the target prestress force. No relevant creep and relaxation were observed as seen in the diagrams.

Test set-up

All the beams were tested under a four-point bending configuration, as shown in Figure 1a, with a constant moment region extended for 1220 mm. Different types of instruments were used to detect the

most relevant physical-mechanical parameters. Strain Gauges on selected top-side and bottom-side GFRP bars, located at the midspan of the specimens, to measure the longitudinal strain in the bars. A load cell was used to monitor the applied load of the actuator. A total of eight string potentiometers were positioned to measure deflection along the length of the beam, placed at mid-section, point-load section, quarter-section, and support. LVDT with a stroke of 50 mm was positioned on the upper side of the mid-span section to measure the strain in compressed concrete. Twelve DEMEC (mechanical strain gages) points were positioned on the lateral face of the beams, equally spaced at 200 mm distance, to measure the strain of concrete at the location of the bars (top and bottom).

Figure 4 - Load (a) and strain (b) profiles during the prestressing of beam GFRP_8M16_2

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Experimental results

The failure modes were observed for each of the tested beam. The experimental results were collected in terms of load vs displacement curves of the tested beams, and by considering the local values of the strain and displacements, during the loading history.

In Figure 5 all the specimens are shown at failure. It can be observed that in all cases, except for GFRP_16M13_1, the failure occurred within the constant moment length. In all cases the rupture was brittle, as expected from the linear behavior up to failure of the GFRP bars. Once the ultimate strain of the glass fibers was reached, the tensile failure of the bars was sudden accompanied by a typical sound of fibers cracking. In GFRP_8M16_1 tensile failure of the GFRP bars anticipated the failure; in GFRP_8M16_2 the failure was contemporary since when the concrete started to crush, tensile failure occurred; in all the other cases tensile failure of the reinforcement was anticipated by crushing of compressed concrete. The ultimate strain of the GFRP bars was computed by adding the initial prestressing strain; due to the application of the flexural load the tensile strain of M13 bars went up to 0.87%, while it reached the ultimate value of 1.04% for M16 bars, at failure. These values should be added to an initial strain of 0.75% (which corresponds to 40% of the ultimate strain of M13 bars) and 0.6% (which corresponds to 36% of the ultimate strain of M16 bars).

The load vs mid-span deflection curves for all the tested beams are shown in Figure 6, where all the curves seem to have the same trend, except for GFRP_16M16_RC. This specimen exhibited a different behaviour since it was the only beam without prestressed reinforcement. By observing the diagrams in Figure 6, the first important finding can be highlighted by considering the different behavior of the beams GFRP_16M16 GFRP_16M16_RC which have the same reinforcement ratio, but with a difference of 36% in prestress level. Even if, as expected, there are not significant differences in terms of load bearing capacity, a major benefit is provided by prestressing technology in terms of service conditions. By considering the performance at the serviceability limit state, it is evident that the presence of the prestressed reinforcement provides higher stiffness due to the total reacting section, without cracking in the entire serviceability range. The deflection of the non-prestressed beam is orders of magnitude greater than the deflection of the prestressed beam under service loads, from what emerges in the observation of the two experimental curves.

In GFRP_16M16_RC concrete crushed first, with a consistent reduction of the load rate; then it maintained substantially constant, but the beam kept deflecting for 80 mm more before the GFRP bars

ruptured. A similar behavior can be observed for the RC beam, but with a considerably reduced extent of the curve between concrete crushing and reinforcement failing. The higher ultimate load reached by the RC beam, approximately the same of the prestressed one, depends on a 20% stronger concrete, as resulted from the compressive test of the cylinders, as reported in Table 2. For all the other prestressed beams, failure occurred almost simultaneously in the compressed concrete and tensioned GFRP bars. The curves also show that by increasing the GFRP reinforcement ratio, the stiffness under service load and the cracking moment of the beams are increased, coherently with the theoretical expectations. In GFRP_8M16 and GFRP_16M13 specimens a pseudo bi-linear trend is evident, which indicates a sharp transition in terms of flexural stiffness after cracking of the concrete and the engagement of the GFRP reinforcement.

Figure 5 - Failure modes of the beams: (a) GFRP_8M16_1, (b) GFRP_8M16_2, (c) GFRP_16M13_1, (d) GFRP_16M13_2, (e) GFRP_16M16, (f) GFRP_16M16_RC

Curves of the applied load vs strain in the GFRP bars were plotted and are shown in Figure 7 for the different types of specimens as indicated in each sub-figure description. It can be deduced from the diagrams in Figure 7 that all the bars, in both sides of the cross section (top and bottom), were in tension up to failure, with a neutral axis just above the line of the top reinforcement. This was the behavior that was desired when the beams were designed, since GFRP bars are particularly weak in compression. As expected those GFRP bars that were located in the bottom side of the cross section exhibited higher tensile strain due to the internal forces that should equilibrate the external flexural moment. The diagram in Figure 8 reports the experimental results in terms of load vs compressive strain of the concrete, as measured from the LVDT readings for specimen GFRP_16M13_2. The experimental curve shows that a significant change in the slope occurred at a load level of about 65 kN, when cracking starts to develop, and stiffness of the compressed concrete decreases. The behavior

appears to be well approximated to a bilinear curve, where an ultimate strain between 0.003 and 0.0035 is reached. This result well matches with the expectations of the theoretical analysis. This curve can be considered representative of the behaviour of all the specimens tested in this experimental study.

Figure 6 - Experimental load vs midspan deflection diagrams

Figure 7 - Experimental values of the Strain in GFRP bars - (a) GFRP_8M16_1; (b) GFRP_16M13_2; (c) GFRP_16M16; (d) GFRP_16M16_RC

Comparison with theoretical results

The theoretical design of the beams started from a sectional analysis that was investigated prior to the experimental tests. In this way it was possible to predict the response of the tested beams under flexural loads. However, it should be mentioned that GFRP bars were not considered in ACI 440.4R at the moment of this experimental programme. According to the assumptions adopted in ACI 440.4R, the mechanical response of the beams was computed in terms of cracking moment, strain in the GFRP reinforcement and ultimate moment. For cracking condition, the ultimate tensile strain of the concrete is known from its ultimate tensile strength. The ultimate strain of compressed concrete was considered to be equal to 0.003. The value of the tendon strain is not known and can be determined from the strain diagram with respect to the strain of concrete using the hypothesis of planar deformations of the cross sections. The neutral axis is localized equilibrating the horizontal forces on the section, and the moments of the internal forces, as typically done in presence of traditional steel reinforcement. The self weight of the PC beams has been considered. The mechanical properties of the FRP bars were taken from Table 1.

Figure 8 - Load vs compressive strain in concrete for GFRP_16M13_2 beam

Assuming a linear behavior of materials under service loads (Figure 9), and stress block for compressed concrete at ultimate (see Figure 10, with a stress equal to $0.85f'_c$), in order to compute the cracking moment and the ultimate moment of the tested beams, the equilibrium equations may be written as follows:

$$C_1 = \frac{1}{2}f_{cc}bc \quad \text{Eq.1}$$

$$C_2 = A'_s(\epsilon'_s - \epsilon_{s0})E_s \quad \text{Eq.2}$$

$$T_1 = \frac{1}{2}f_{ct}b(h - c) \quad \text{Eq.3}$$

$$T_2 = A_s(\epsilon_{s0} + \epsilon_s)E_s \quad \text{Eq.4}$$

$$M_{cr} = C_1 \frac{2}{3}c + C_2(c - d') + T_1 \frac{2}{3}(h - c) + T_2(d - c) \quad \text{Eq.5}$$

Figure 9 - Sectional hypothesis for the computation of the cracking moment

$$C_1 = 0,85f_c b a \quad \text{Eq.6}$$

$$T_1 = A'_s (\varepsilon_{s0} + \varepsilon'_s) E_s \quad \text{Eq.7}$$

$$T_2 = A_s (\varepsilon_{s0} + \varepsilon_s) E_s \quad \text{Eq.8}$$

$$M_u = C_1 \left(c - \frac{a}{2} \right) + T_1 (d' - c) + T_2 (d - c) \quad \text{Eq.9}$$

Figure 10 - Sectional hypothesis for the computation of the ultimate moment

where: b = cross section width; h = cross section depth; d = distance from extreme compression fiber to centroid of bottom reinforcement; d' = distance from extreme compression fiber to centroid of top reinforcement; c = neutral axis depth; f_{cc} = concrete compressive strength; f_{ct} = concrete tensile strength; A_s = reinforcement area in the bottom side; A'_s = reinforcement area in the top side; M_{cr} = cracking moment; M_u = ultimate moment; E_s = longitudinal elastic modulus of FRP.

Table 2 shows the main experimental results compared to the theoretical predictions. The load P is the prestressing force applied to the GFRP bars; f_{cj} is the compressive strength of concrete as measured from cylinders in laboratory tests on testing day; f_{ctj} is tensile strength of concrete as measured from prisms subjected to three point bending tests, on testing day; ε'_s and ε_s are the ultimate strain of the top and bottom GFRP bars, respectively, at the midspan of the cross-section; F_{cr} is the cracking load; F_u is the ultimate load; δ_u is the experimental value of the ultimate displacement at mid span.

As visible from Table 2, the comparison between the theoretical values of the ultimate load and the experimental outcomes shows that the analytical prediction can be considered accurate, since the maximum error falls within a range of 6%.

Table 2: Comparison between experimental results and theoretical predictions

Specimen	Pre-tension Force P	Concrete Strength		Section Analysis					Test Results				
		f_{cj} MPa	f_{ctj} MPa	c^* mm	ε'_s^* %	ε_s^* %	F_{cr} kN	F_u kN	ε'_s^* %	ε_s^* %	F_{cr} kN	F_u kN	δ_u mm
GFRP_16M16 	925	38.6	5.3	64	-0.02	0.61	85.0	167.9	0.04	0.80	48.0	158.7	179
GFRP_16M16_RC 	0	49.2	4.6	38	0.18	1.22	47.6	167.2	0.24	0.87	8.9	172.8	262
GFRP_16M13_1 	649	35.6	4.5	53	0.04	0.79	66.3	133.8	0.13	0.68	54.7	136.9	146
GFRP_16M13_2 	667	44.0	4.6	47	0.08	0.93	68.2	150.6	-	0.60	63.2	157.2	129
GFRP_8M16_1 	463	35.6	4.5	44	0.11	1.00	58.7	117.3	0.15	1.00	37.4	114.3	153
GFRP_8M16_2 	463	44.0	4.6	39	0.16	1.17	59.9	131.2	0.2	1.04	46.7	128.1	148

* values that are computed with reference to the ultimate limit state

In order to further evaluate the flexural behavior of the tested beams, a theoretical vs experimental comparison was carried out in terms of moment-curvature diagrams. The use of an ultimate deflection /service deflection ratio gives a warning that anticipate the brittle failure of such structural elements. This is an important issue that should be discussed in view of new design provisions since the concept of ductility that is found in the case of steel reinforcement, is not applicable in this context. For this reason, in Figure 11, the moment-curvature curve is shown for brevity only for the GFRP_16M13_1 and GFRP_16M13_2 specimens, computed by a theoretical sectional analysis and by the experimental readings of the subsequent positions of the DEMEC points (placed in the constant moment region) as:

$$\chi_i = \left[\max\left(\frac{L_i - L_0}{L_0}\right) - \min\left(\frac{L_i - L_0}{L_0}\right) \right] \cdot \frac{1}{H} \quad \text{Eq.10}$$

where: L_i = horizontal distance between DEMEC points at stage i ; L_0 = initial distance between the points; H = vertical distance between the points, 127 mm.

The experimental results showed a good agreement with the theoretical predictions, as shown in Figure 11. Since the GFRP is an elastic material, the moment-curvature behavior will take a bilinear shape. This response is observed in the theoretical curve obtained and the graphical trend of the experimental curve. The cracking of the concrete is represented by the inflection point on the figure. Since it was not possible to collect data from the DEMEC points in the last part of the loading history, the ultimate point was not captured. However, an estimation of its values could be obtained theoretically through a sectional analysis of the beam, as shown in Figure 14. The prediction of the cracking moment could be improved by considering a reduction of the tensile strength of concrete in beams, respect to small scale specimens, as found in Bielak et al. (2020).

Figure 11 - Theoretical and experimental moment vs curvature diagrams:
(a) GFRP_16M13_1; (b) GFRP_16M13_2

CONCLUSIONS

With a view to preserving the durability of reinforced concrete constructions in very aggressive environments, the proposal to use FRP reinforcement instead of traditional ribbed steel is an opportunity that deserves to be further explored in the field of research. Since carbon fibers still have a higher cost, compared to glass fibers, on the latter falls the choice in terms of cost-effectiveness. Since, however, glass fibers are also subject to chemical and physical degradation in contact with hostile external agents, then the use of prestressing technology may prove profitable in increasing the service life of GFRP-reinforced beams.

The present research, which is mainly experimental in nature, reports interesting results obtained on six full-scale beams reinforced entirely with GFRP bars and stirrups, five of which were prestressed by prestressing the longitudinal GFRP reinforcements. Two different diameters of GFRP bars were

used: 13 mm and 16 mm; in addition, the beams were reinforced with different configurations and different levels of bar pre-tensioning, depending on the reinforcement used. One of the beams was reinforced with the same reinforcement as one of the remaining five, but without applying any prestressing force. The research allowed experimentation and calibration of the tensioning stages, which in the case of the 13-mm bars showed some criticalities, although the tensioning force was always kept below 40% of the ultimate load of the GFRP bars.

The pre-tensioning technique used was the same as for traditional prestressing steel reinforcement. Continuous monitoring of the strain in GFRP bars and the pre-tensioning load was conducted during pre-tensioning process. Based on what has been observed, M13 GFRP bars can exhibit failure at chuck location during or following the jacking phase. This issue could be avoided by using an industrial prestressing equipment pulling all bars at the same time, thus avoiding the repetitions of hand operations that may damage the bars (as hammering of the chucks for removal). However, based on the obtained results, conventional prestressing equipment can be considered suitable for this non traditional material with orthotropic behaviour.

The flexural tests highlighted the brittle behavior at failure, caused by the tensile rupture of the GFRP bars. Due to the absence of plastic behaviour, elastic deformability assumes a key role in defining a warning factor prior to brittle failure. Visual warning before collapse, evidencing diffused cracks and large deformations, was obtained limiting the initial strain to 40% of the ultimate strain, which also guarantees less creep and relaxation. In this case, the strain capacity was always more than 0.6%, which exceeds the threshold of 0.5% set by current standards for conventional PC.

From the comparison with experimental data, the test results are in good agreement with the analytical predictions in terms of ultimate moment and load capacity of the beams. Although higher errors can be found in some cases, for the cracking moment.

As a final consideration, mild-prestressed concrete elements with GFRP reinforcement represent a promising solution for those applications where a non-corrosive technology is needed, basing on the mechanical properties performed in this experimental campaign, the allowable cost of the material and the adaptability to the conventional prestressing equipment could easily allow a production on a large scale in real applications.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.